

(CASE REPORT)

A case study: An ayurvedic management of Urdhwaga *Amlapitta* with special reference to hyperacidity

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Abstract

Vitiation of *Agni* in *Amashaya* (stomach) region due to various reasons causes *Amlapitta*. Some of the common *Pitta* vitiating factors are fasting, eating between meals, worry, hurry, spicy food etc. These factors derange the *Pachaka Pitta* (digestive enzymes etc.) and as a result *Pachaka pitta* vitiates. Thus developed condition is called *Amlapitta*. Hydrochloric acid (HCl) when not utilized well, or when produced in large quantity in the stomach region causes inflammation of stomach (gastric = related to stomach), that is called gastritis. This can derange the digestive procedures. The increased or normal level of HCl can destroy the soft tissue (epithelium) lining of esophagus, stomach, duodenum etc. If not managed on time this can give rise to ulceration (breach in tissue). Usually the esophageal sphincter muscle contracts thus preventing the stomach acid from shooting up into the esophagus, but if this muscle are not functioning properly, the acid can slip past it and this is when heartburn symptoms start, which is called Gastroesophageal reflux.

Due to lifestyle changes and changes in food habits people are mainly suffering from GIT disorders. *Amlapitta* among them is a most commonly seen disease. This article is a case study of a 40 years male patient with signs & symptoms of *Urdhwaga Amlapitta*. Patient was treated with ayurvedic medicine and principles of Ayurveda according to *Rogavastha* and *Doshavastha*. This case study shows potential of ayurveda and it proves ayurveda has evidence based treatment. In this case study patient of *Urdhwaga Amlapitta* was treated with *Shamana Aushadhi* according to his *Prakruti*, *Dosha*, *Dhatu* and *Mala*. Rapid but steady improvement in patient's complaints.

Keywords: *Urdhwaga Amlapitta*, *pitta*, Hyperacidity, *Shamana*, *Mandagni*

1. Introduction

"*Rogo sarveapi mandeagnau*" Acharya Vagbhaṭa has described that all the diseases are caused by *Mandagni*. In Ayurved main cause of all disease is *Mandagni*^[1] (less digestive power). *Amlapitta* (Hyperacidity) is very common disease encountered in present population with more or less severity. Generally 80% of the top ten life threatening diseases in the world are due to inappropriate dietary habits^[2]. Present lifestyle has become sedentary, lack of physical activity, unhealthy food habits have led to many GI diseases. Now a days, mostly the young people are being diagnosed with *Amlapitta*. Ayurveda states that *Amlapitta* is due to *Sama Pitta* and increase in *Amla*, *Drava* and *Ushna Guna* of *Pitta*^[3]. It is also said that eating and fasting during indigestion leads to Acidity, heart burn, gastritis which is referred as *Amlapitta*^[4].

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According to *Gati*, *Amlapitta* is classified into *Urdhwaga* and *Adhoga Amlapitta*^[5]. According to *Dosha* it is classified as *Vatanubandhi*, *Kaphanubandhi* and *Vatkaphanubandhi*. Acharya Sushruta has enlisted *Katu* as original *Rasa* of *Pitta* and mentioned that when *Pitta* becomes *vidagdha* then its *Rasa* changes to *Amla Rasa*^[6]. Acharya Charaka has not mentioned *Amlapitta* as separate disease but described it in *Grahani* (digestive disorder) as one of its *lakshana*^[7].

Most of Digestive diseases like Dyspepsia, Hyperacidity, Gastritis etc. can be included under *Amlapitta* in Ayurveda^[8]. In ancient classical text Charak Samhita, *Amlapitta* was described as a symptom^[9]. Acharya Kashyapa was the first who mentioned the disease *Amlapitta* in a separate chapter and he has also mentioned *Manasika Bhava* as a chief cause of this disease. He also mentioned the analysis of *Amlapitta* on the basis of *Dosha*. Acharya Kashyapa believed that the disease is caused by vitiation of *Tridoshas* causing *Mandagni* leading to *Vidagdha* ultimately manifesting as *Amlapitta*^[10]. Madhava Acharya has mentioned excess consumption of non-vegetarian food and *Vidahi Annapana* (foods which cause burning sensation inside) as cause of *Amlapitta*^[11].

In *Amlapitta* the root cause is *Agnimandya* and formation of *Aama*. So, while treating *Amlapitta* mainly, *Agnideepak* and *Aamapachak* drugs are used. *Tikta Rasapradhan* drugs are commonly *Aamapachak* & *Agnideepak*^[12]. In this case study 40 years male patient came to OPD with complaints of *Avipaka, Clama, Hrullas, Hastapad chimchimayan, Kanthdaha, Aruchi, paridaha, Amlodgar, Kshudhamandya, Adhmana, Daurballya* since one year. He was taking Allopathy medicines for same complaints since one year but he did not get relief completely. Hence patient came to OPD for Ayurvedic treatment. This case was challenging to treat because patient had done Endoscopy from another hospital which showed H. Pylori positive. After taking his detailed history and examination patient was treated according to *Vyadhiavastha* and *Doshavastha*. At the end of treatment, H. Pylori infection of the patient came negative.

Objectives

- To study *Amlapitta Vyadhi* in detail with the help of case.
- To study treatment principles/ *Siddhanta* / Protocol of Ayurveda.

2. Case History

2.1. Present illness

40 years, Male, C/O *Avipaka, Clama, Hrullas, hastapad chimchimayan, Kanthdaha, Aruchi, Paridaha, Amlodgar, Kshudhamandya, Adhmana, Daurbalya* since one year. Past illness: No history of any major medical or surgical illness.

Medication history: Not Specific.

- On examination PR- 80/min
- BP- 130/80 mm of Hg
- RS- B/L clear
- SPO2- 98% on Room air
- CVS- S1S2 Normal
- CNS- Conscious and Oriented
- P/A- Soft and nontender

2.2. Ashtavidha pariksha

- *Nadi* : *Pitta Kaphaja*
- *Mal*: *Samyaka*
- *Mutra*: *Samyaka*
- *Jivha*: *Sama*
- *Nidan Panchak*
- *Hetu*: *Ahara* : *Atikatu Aahar (Spicy), Ati Amla Aahara, Akal Bhojan, Adhyashan.*
- *Vihara* : *Ratraujagran, Diwaswap.*
- *Samprapti* ^[13]:

Hetu sevan → *Tridosha Prakopa (Pitta Pradhana)*

→ *Agnimandya* → *Anna Vidagdha* → *Pittataprakop* (vitiation) → *Amla* and *Drava Guna* dominance → *Amlapitta*.

2.3. Samprapti Ghatak

2.3.1. Doshā

Pitta Pradhana, Kapha anubandhi.

2.3.2. Dushya

Rasa Dushti.

2.3.3. Strotodushti

Annavaha Strotas, Purishvaha Strotas, Rasavaha Strotas.

2.3.4. Vyadhi Avastha

Sama Avastha, Doshā Urdhwagati

2.3.5. Sadhyasadhyatva

Kashta Sadhya

2.3.6. Vyadhimarga

AbhyantarMarga

2.3.7. Vyadhi Nidana

Urdhwaga Amlapitta, Samawastha Doshā Urdhwagati.

2.4. Treatment (Chikitsa)

While treating *Amlapitta* we must think about *Doshadhikya*, *Sthanvaigunya* and *Hetu* of the patient then plan treatment accordingly like *Pachan* and *Anuloman*.

This patient of *Amlapitta* was unable to digest properly leading to inappropriate *Rasa Dhatu* formation. So a *Rasayan* drug was added first i.e. *Guduchighana Vati*, *Guduchi* also reduce *Samta*. Other Drugs included in treatment i.e. *Pravalpanchamrut Vati*. *Avipattikar Choorna*, *Hingvashtak Choorna*, *Raktapachak choorna* reduce *doshā samata* and leads to *anulomana* and *shamana* of *doshā*. *Shankha Bhasma* helps *Deepana*, *Pachan*, *Pittahara*, *Dravata*.

2.5. Pathyapathya

2.5.1. Pathya

Yava, *Godhuma*, *Mudga*, old rice, boiled and cooled water, *Sharkara*, *Madhu*, *Sattu*, all bitter and light vegetables, *Vruddha Kushmanda*, *Dadima*, *Patol*^[14].

2.5.2. Apathya

Seesame, blackgram, garlic, curd, amla and Katu padarth, Guru Anna, oily and spicy food, fermented foods^[15].

2.6. Observation

Table 1 Case summary with follow up

	Clinical features	Treatment (Chikitsa)
Day 1	Avipaka, Clama, Hrullas, Hastapad Chimchimayan, Kanthdaha, Aruchi, Paridaha, Amlodgar, Kshudhamandya, Adhmana, Daurbalya since 1year	Guduchighan Vati 2 tds, Praval Panchamrut Vati 2 tds, Avipattikar Choorn, Raktapachak choorna each 200 mg, Shankhbhasma 100 mg tds, Kushmandavleha 1 tablespoon tds.

1st follow up (7 th day)	symptoms relief 50%, Kshudhmandya, Adhmana, Katishoola	Guduchighan Vati 2 tds, Praval Panchamrut Vati 2 tds, Asthimajjapachak Choorna, Avipattikar choorn,Raktapachak Choorna each 200 mg, Hingvashtak choorna 100 mg tds, Kushmandavleha 1 tablespoon tds
2nd follow up (14 th day)	Symptoms relief 80%	Guduchighan Vati 2 tds, Praval Panchamrut Vati 2 tds Asthimajjapachak Choorna,Raktapachak Choorna,each 200 mg, Hingvashtak Choorna 100 mg tds, Kushmandavleha 1 tablespoon tds.

3. Discussion

Amlapitta is caused due to increase in Drava and Amla Guna of Pitta. Patient was given *Guduchighan Vati* as *Rasayana*. While other drugs for *Shaman of Pitta Dosha*. On 7th day after treatment started patient had 50% relief of symptoms of *Amlapitta*. On regular follow up decrease in symptoms gradually decreased.

Patient was taking treatment for last one year, Ayurvedic as well as Allopathic medicine but did not get relief then he came to OPD for only Ayurvedic Medicine. In Ayurvedic science before starting the treatment patient's thorough examination in view of *Dosha, Nadi, Prakruti* etc. should be done.

This patient was given with *Guduchighan Vati* and *Anulomaka* drugs for the *Dosha* which aggregated *Urdhwagati* and *Urdhwa Amashaya*. One *Rasayan* drug added in view of his health became very poor because of improper digestion. Then he has been given with combination of *Anulomaka Dravya* such as *Hingvashtak choorna, Avipattikar Choorna* and *Sheet Dravya RaktaPachaka, Shankha Bhasma, Kushmandavleha*.

3.1. Probable mode of action of drugs

- *Guduchighana Vati*- It is *Tikta Rasatmak, Swadupaka* and acts as *Rasayana, Jwaraghna, Pachana*.
- *Praval Panchamrut Vati*^[16]-*Pittaghna,swadurasatmak,Shamak,Pachak,AgniPradipak*.
- *Shankha Bhasma* is indicated in initial stage of *Amlapitta*. *Shankha Bhasma* is *Deepana, Pachana, Grahi, Pittahara*.
- *Hingvashtaka Choorna*-It is *Deepana, Pachana*.
- *Raktapachak Choorna*- It is *Pittashamaka, Anulomak*.
- *Asthimajjapachak Choorna*-It is *Pachaka and Pittaghna*.
- *Avipattikar Choorna*- It is *Pittashamak, Anulomaka*, useful in *Amlapitta*.
- *Kushmandavleha*- It is *Madhur-Katu Rasa,Pittavatshaman,Samashitoshn Virya*.

4. Conclusion

Shamana Upakram as above with *Pathyahara* for long period of time are beneficial for any GI related disease. According to Ayurveda principles patient of any disease treated with their *Dosha, Dhatu, Mala Avastha* and *Ashtavidha Pariksha* definitely leads to *Upashaya*. In this casestudy, *Shamana Chikitsa* with *Pathyapathya* proven to be beneficial in reducing the signs and symptoms of *Urdhwaga Amlapitta*.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there was no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this manuscript.

Statement of informed consent

Written informed consent was taken from patient.

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